

The Significance of Harmonization in Natural Environment and Cultural Environment

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to present the essential role of the harmonization between nature and culture from the perspective of Myanmar environmental thought. The concept of harmonization plays an indispensable and significant role in various areas of philosophy. The research problem is "Why the harmonization between nature and culture can be considered as a way of overcoming some crisis of human society?" Because of the human being needs, a greatly fulfillment its influence culture and can be the damage of nature. Everyone should be respected and considered everything that is all living beings and non-living beings. This paper is used method and evaluative method. This paper will contribute towards understanding the importance of ethical value for environmental conservation and sustainable development.

Keywords: Harmonization, Nature, Culture.

Introduction

Human being lives in two worlds, namely, natural and cultural worlds. Natural world means natural surrounding or natural environment. Natural surrounding or environment is the earth planet itself, including forests, mountains, rivers and seas. Cultural surrounding is man-made. Both surroundings are essential and indispensable for human beings. In the contemporary period the whole people face with the challenges and issues concerning environment. So, environmental conservation is necessary for lasting benefit of the earth. Only man can save and conserve the loose of the natural environment.

Human population growth may be seen to set at the root of all of the world's environmental problems. Increasingly large numbers of people are being added to the world every year. As the number of people increases, more pollution is generated, are used up. Including Myanmar, most of the countries faced with natural environment deteriorating and climate change problems all over the world. The problems which faced is a main challenge for the living world to be continuous development and to decrease poverty.

Moreover, as Myanmar, for the long term continuous progress, to improve three main pivots: economic, social and environmental conservation and to face with today environmental challenges together with the international moving towards that is currently changing. So, these changes need harmonization in natural environment and cultural environment. Human beings have fundamental needs. Because of these can be the damage of natural environment.

Natural Environment

Environment may be defined as "What surrounds and surrounding". These constituents genetically fall into two groups:

- (a) Natural environment, consisting of all constituents of natural origin likes physiography, climate, soil, water, wild animals and minerals; and
- (b) Cultural environment, consisting of all elements having human touch in their origin which includes all manifestation of human activates.

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The word 'nature' is derived from the Latin word 'natural', or essential qualities, innate disposition, and in ancient times, literally means 'birth'. Nature was a Latin translation of the Greek word physics which originally related to the intrinsic characteristics that plants, animals, and other features of the world develop of their own accord.

Nature, in the broadest sense, is equivalent to the natural, physical, or material world or universe. Nature refers to the phenomena of the physical world, and also to life in general. Nature is a concept with two major sets of interrelation meanings, referring on the one hand to the things which are natural, or subject to the normal working of "law of nature", or on the other hand to the essential properties and causes of those things to be what they naturally are, or in other words the law of nature themselves.

Within the various uses of the word today, nature often refers to geology and wildlife. Nature may refer to general realm of various types of living plants and animals, and in some cases to the processes associated with inanimate objects the way that particular types of things exist and change of their own accord, such as the weather and geology of the earth, and the matter and energy of which all these things are composed. It is often taken to mean the "nature environment" or wilderness with animals, rocks, forest, beaches, and in general those things that have not been substantially altered by human intervention, or which persist despite human intervention. For example, manufactured objects and human interaction generally are not considered part of nature, unless qualified as, "human nature" or "the world of nature". This more traditional concept of natural things which can still be found today implies a distribution between the natural and the artificial, with the artificial being understood as which has been brought into being by a human consciousness or a human mind.

Natural environment means all living and non-living things that are naturally on Earth. The natural environment encompasses all living and non-living things occurring naturally on Earth or some region thereof. It is an environment that encompasses the interaction of all living spaces.

Climate, weather, and natural resources affect human survival and economic activity. The concept of natural environment can be distinguished by components. Complete ecological units that function as natural systems without massive civilized human intervention, including all vegetation, microorganisms, soil, rocks, atmosphere, and natural phenomena that occur within their boundaries and their nature.

Cultural Environment

The various elements of culture fall into two general categories material cultural and non-material culture. Material culture consists of all the physical objects or artifacts, made or used by people. Non-material culture consists of those things that have no physical existence such as language, ideas, knowledge and behavior.

Material culture and non-material culture are closely interrelated. For example, many modern appliances are products of advanced technological knowledge. Moreover, material culture shapes non-material culture. For instance, television and computer deliver vast amounts of information.

Culture is a very complex phenomenon that can be expressed in an infinite number of ways. Accordingly, it would be impossible to describe all aspects of any single culture. However, it is possible to isolate certain components that are common to all cultures. These include beliefs, values, norms and language.

Culture of society implies its general way of life. A society is an organized group of individuals. Culture thus implies a general behavior pattern of a society. Culture refers to all that man has acquired as a member of society. Culture is a powerful human for survival, but it is fragile phenomenon. It is constantly changing and easily last because it exists only in human minds. Human beings written languages, governments, buildings, and other man-made things are merely the products of culture.

The environment that is influenced by human can be called "the built environment" or cultural landscape. For instance, today, each of the country in the world has been to become strong for four bases: economic, politics, education and social; in constructing as country that can improve its people's living and social standard, advanced, and strong power.

Myanmar has been establishing in above four powers, in economic section; it is the basic policy fact, based on the agriculture, to construct for the improvement of other economic sections. In establishing the advanced country, it must materialize for the industrial and handicraft sections whatever it may be. The section of industrialized works that based on agriculture is one of the Myanmar's essential sections. Therefore, now it has been implementing practically to the aim from traditional manual land for cultivation forward industrialized land for cultivation. Myanmar has established many infrastructures: economic, social affairs and transportation communication that needed for the country economic development so in the industrialized section: there would have been many good prospects to improve with acceleration.

Developing the industrial works like that, supported many for the countries economic and people living and dwelling. According to the population growth, it had found that factories and workshops mixed up with number of houses in which the people lived. Moreover, because of the polluted water and air that can cause pollution that discarded from the factories.

Therefore, for the development of the industrial works, there has good potentialities for the people like that on the other hand; the people will suffer bad effects that appeared health problems and environmental pollution. Hence, everyone must discard systematically to the discarded materials that can cause pollution. Therefore, only when there was improvement of the factory works, there would conserve the environmental pollution.

Similarly, large dams can also block the flow of nutrients, which in turn, can reduce agricultural yield. Reduced agricultural productivity would that be devastating for the country. Some international observers have attributed this to the Myitsone Dam construction. Such conflicts can father threaten food security since they displace thousands of people who then struggled to rebuild their livelihoods. Because of the human beings constructions access road, bridges, dams and factories, they influenced culture. When culture over when the nature can cause damage. So, because of the human being needs, the importance of did not damage the natural environment.

The Conception of "To Meet the Needs, To Keep the Balance"

There are many theories in psychology and fields that to identify and explain person's universal human needs. The most predominate theory on human drives is the evolution theory which simplifies person's needs to survive and procreation. These two needs generate a wide range of other secondary needs pursuit of the two primary ones. For example, the needs to develop social bonds are included in the evolutionary theory as a tool to help people survive and procreate.

Form people understanding most other theories look at virtually the same needs in which subcategories or different perspectives, which can be more or less practical when exploring ways to enrich human lives. But ultimate the majority of the theories basic on human needs include the same requirements, with more or less emphasis put on the various components.

In their purest form, person universal human needs:

1. Physical needs (having food, water, and shelter, sleep and health)
2. Safety (physical safety, social safety, self-concept safety)
3. Social needs (having a sense of belonging, feeling connected to other, having friend, love and intimacy.)
4. Self-concept (knowing oneself, having confidence, constant growth, having purpose, feeling special, contributing something to the world)
5. Freedom (having control, having choices, having variety).

Physical needs are the basic needs everyone needs in order to stay alive and be healthy.

Safety needs refers to one needs to feel safe. The importance of feeling safe becomes really salient when it is threatened. Imagine being unsure of one's physical safety. (Example: at time of war), one's social safety (example: the threat of losing one's friends), or self-image safety (example: doubting one's worth and capabilities).

Everybody is social animals and depends on the presence and support of other to survive and thrive. The importance of human's social needs is also very salient when one imagines their absence. For example, imagine not having family, not having friends, or feeling socially excluded from a group.

Self-concept refers to one's imagine of oneself and is necessary for having purpose in one's life. Everyone all have a need to feel special in some way, even if everyone has a very strong need to belong in a group. As much as people went to please others, everyone all also went to stand out and be different in person own way. This means knowing who everyone and a person value.

One need for freedom allows everyone to have variety and opportunities. It allows everyone to have access to things that enable everyone to live and to grow.

This classification is the simplest but at the same time still practical and comprehensive way of looking at one basic human need. All five categories are interrelated which means that each category depends on the other to be complete and no one category is necessarily above any other.

The degree of need for each category varies. What each category to one might differ from the person next to one. There is a reason why there are many theories and perspectives on basic human needs. Because of there is no strict formula for it. But what is constant is the need for each five category to be addressed to a certain degree in order to have the prerequisite of living a balanced, happy and fulfilled life. This is what means by everyone all have the same basic needs, but can go about reaching them indifferent ways.

One's idea of fulfillment of each category is going to depend on one value, where one is in one life, and one's environment. For example, the important of having food and water is paramount for every individual. However, one can see how even this need can be secondary to another, such as the need for freedom or even self-concept in some cases.

One's basic needs are all interrelated. It is important not to neglect any of the categories because they are interrelated, therefore neglecting one can have a cascade effect on the others. The importance of each basic need can be look at it discretely, but in reality, each basic is in some way connected to the others.

For example, One's physical need is interrelated to one's safety needs. One needs to have food and water in order to have the energy to protect oneself at time of safety. And vise-versa without safety, one's physical needs are threatened and can be taken way. Social bonds can help one get and protect the resources one need to survive and stay healthy.

As another example, the need for freedom is interrelated to the need for a positive self-concept as it allows for the inclusion of variety and growth in one's life. Also by having freedoms, one has more choices and variety to choose friends who give one confidence and improve one's self-concept. In addition, the need for freedom can help one feel safer because one has more variety, which means if one of one's resources gets taken away one have other options.

The example noted above is just some of many ways that one's need is dependent on one another. But this does not mean that one have to perfectly meet all of these requirements at any given time, and compensating is a practical way of finding the best way that works for one. But it is essential that one at least address each of categories at some point in one's life (and to a satisfactory level) to achieve a balance.

Man is a rational animal. So, rational begins are also much have morality and ethics. Ethics is the field of study concerned with human conduct. In ordinary language, ethics and morality are often used interchangeably. However morality refers to judgments' and actions regarding what is good and right and ethics provides answers to why such judgments and actions are considered good and right. So, with regard to an ethics of environmental conservation it will refer to disciplined reflection about morality, moral problems and moral judgments about the environment.

Ethics brings an awareness of the role of values in human activity and that such values are determined by culture. The moral values and cognitive beliefs of a culture play a crucial role in how well human societies view the natural environment and how they utilize it. What are the moral codes woven into cultures-what are they and how do they function to enhance or distort the relationships of human beings to one another and to the Earth? There is a new appreciation of the way in which moral ideas motivate persons to care for the world around them and these moral ideals and values are found in the many diverse cultures.

Conclusion

Human being lives in two worlds, namely, the world of nature and the world of culture. The world of nature is considered as the primary environment for human beings and the world of culture, secondary environment.

From the perspective of philosophical anthropology, human beings have three fundamental needs such as nutrition, clothing and shelter. Besides these fundamental needs man has more other needs which may be called spiritual needs or mental needs, such as aesthetical needs. To fulfill both spiritual and physical needs human beings depend on natural surroundings. Everyone can get raw materials to build shelter such as bamboos, woods from forest and mountain. So forest and mountains are benefactors for human beings. Although human beings use the product of nature to fulfill the cultural needs, some of them of nature act without disciplines. The people who lack the knowledge of environment do everything on

nature as they wish. Because of their bad actions on natural environment the disadvantages appear. To eliminate their bad actions the educated persons make them to be aware of the environmental situations.

Nowadays, the earth and living beings all over the world are threatened by climate change and natural disasters. Moreover, other living beings especially rare animals are in danger because of selfish human beings. The reason for the climate change is harmful to the public benefits is that for agriculture, when in some region is longing for rain; it is appearing problems that face with overflowing and farmlands drowning. Such as those processes of events are the bad results of climate changes.

Whether it may be, because natural disaster is the process of events that cannot avoid, it must fact with and suffers. Therefore, everyone must do preparations how to overcome the natural disasters that will become. Human being lives between in competition with opposite nature and culture. By living such as, continue to exist the ecosystem in the long-term, it is important in harmony with the nature and culture. If everyone gives preference and lives not to damage the nature, everyone will remain living out-of-date in the ancient human community. The developed human society must live in breast of time with appropriately. If everyone gives preference and lives to the culture, the culture will influence so all living beings and non-living beings in the world will die and damage. So, the maxim adopted by the human community for environmental conservation and sustainable development is "to meet the need, to keep the balance". The maxim point out is people to keep the balance between environmental conservation and their daily life to fulfill their needs. So, nature and culture in harmony within environment are essential for environmental conservation and sustainable development.

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